

Experimental Enhancement of Bio Gas Production from Industrial Wastage

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ABSTRACT

The present work investigates the biogas production was performed using Industrial wastage. The laboratory experiment was conducted in floating drum type anaerobic digester capacity of 1m³ made of fiber material at continues process. The cow dung used as an inoculum of the anaerobic digester. Then raw material feeded as a waste in two state one wet and dry wastage 1:1 waste/water equal ratio and fermentation process at 30°C to 35°C was maintained in mesophilic condition. The initial pH, biogas yield, Methane concentration, and HRT these parameters was studied in the experiments. The maximum biogas yield was 0.68m³ and methane concentration was reached in 67%. The maximum biogas production reported as 30min in meso philic condition using inflammable time. The pH maximum level of 7.1 and end of the digestion period \pH (acid production) was decreased. HRT days calculated as 45 days.

KEYWORDS: Anaerobic digestion, Renewable energy, Industrial waste, wet waste, Dry waste, fermentation, HRT

I. INTRODUCTION

Anaerobic digestion (AD) is a biochemical and thermochemical process for the treating of organic matter such as sewage sludge and industrial effluents, animal wastes, agro wastes. The anaerobic digestion process producing biogas having four stages of digestion process it's like hydrolysis, acid genesis, actogenesis, methane genesis in this first stage hydrolysis process involves convert complex organics to sugars and amines. The second stage involves in Convert the sugar to organic acids to acetic acids. The End digestion period the conversion of acetic acid into methane and carbon dioxide the methano genic phase [1]. Generally the biogas contains 50-70% methane CH₄ and 30-50% carbon dioxides CO₂ depending upon these substrates or organic and also some small amount of other gases like hydrogen sulphide. The CH₄ is the component chiefly available for is general calorific value of 21-24MJ/M³ [2]. The biogas technologies mostly apply natural anaerobic bacteria for microbes major communities form an intricate microbiological and cod for food chain mechanisms it's mainly population of dynamics of natural ecosystems [3]. Biogas as a fuel in any country for used in mainly heating purpose and cooking then purified biogas used in a gas engine to covert the electricity and heat[4].The gases methane, and hydrogen produced, can be combusted [5].These study of biogas production system having main advantages of eliminating greenhouse gas, betterment of fertilizer and production of power and heat [6].

Generally bio digester can be operated on their temperatures ranges (a)psycho piles below 28°C (b)mesophilic medium temperature at 29 to 40°C (c)thermo philic at 50 to 55°C[7].The methane genesis and microorganisms growth is mainly depend on various parameters like pH, temperature, C/N ratio, organic loading rate, reactor design, inoculums and HRT [8].The now a days anaerobic treatment plants of solid waste and sludge wastes are using merging of heat treatment leading to lower amounts and higher for sludge to biogas production in end of digestion process[9]. The dry fermentation process like dry press mud is a very complex and more reliable for the biochemical process. It's very critical to produce CH₄ to adopt suitable digestion process with various factors [10]. AS a result, this study

uses industrial waste like press mud in different state for fermentation to generate biogas and find optimum biogas production in wet and dry press mud and different parameters temperature, pressure and acid production.

II. MATERIAL AND METHODS

The laboratory scale anaerobic digestion experiments were carried out with two phases, one dry and other wet wastage. The two variable temperatures and pressures are monitored. Thermocouples were used to measure the temperature of digester slurry. Pressure gauge was used to pressure measurement. The press mud was collected from sugar industry in sethiyathope. Gas flows were measured using with gas flow meter. Inoculums of cow dung were collected from dairy form and cow dung dried in sunlight then crushed mechanically. The inflammation time was measured using lab scale burner. The physical and chemical properties of press mud shown in table .1.

Table.1. physical and chemical properties of Industrial Wastage

Crude wax	5-14%
Fiber	15-30%
Sugar	5-15%
SiO	4-10%
Mgo	0.5-1.5%
pH	6 to 8
Crude protein	5-15%
Moisture	75%

III. EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

The bioreactor with a capacity of 1m³ made up of fibre material. A batch study was carried out in floating drum anaerobic bioreactor. The effective volume of the bioreactor was maintained at 700 litres. This reactor was properly provided with suitable arrangements for feeding, gas collection and draining of residues. In this experiments were carried out in the mesospheric temperature range. The bioreactor was initially inoculated with 40kgs cow dung and same quantity of water was added. Then feedstock selected

for the experiment was wet waste and dry waste were collected from industry. The bioreactor was charged separately for wet and dry waste at 30kgs for each and water was added. The final slurry of reactor used as a bio-fertilizer. Daily biogas production was measured by using gas flow meter (GI).

Fig.1 schematic view of the Experimental Setup

The above fig.1 shows that schematic view of this experimental setup. The bioreactor was mixed by pneumatic stirrer with agitated the digester slurry with help of air compressor for swirling twice in a day. The pH was measured using digital pH redox meter. These daily and cumulative methane generations monitored and analyzed in AVL DI gas analyzer 444 used as a gas chromatography.

IV. RESULT AND DISCUSSIONS

Fig.2. Biogas yield in HRT days.

In this research biogas generation was calculated from biogas yield producing in the bio reactor during the Hydro retention time (HRT) in days. Fig.1 shows the biogas yield from bioreactor wet waste gave very low percentage of gas production compare to dry waste because of wet press mud having C/N ratio is less than 18. The microorganisms are decreased reason for this lowest source of nutrition and Carbon/Nitrogen ratio. The dry waste having higher daily gas production compare to wet waste in hydro retention time.

Fig.3. Methane (CH4) in HRT days

The wet waste having low carbon content and acid formation pH level was 5.8 so methane formation is very low compare to dry waste. The microbes present in mine water with dry waste because higher methane production 67% was achieved. This methane (CH₄) was obtained at 30°C in mesophilic condition.

Fig.4. Acid formation (pH)

The acid reduction (pH) in these stage acetogenic bacteria is converting to organic material to organic acids so slowly increased for pH and also reducing the methane concentration were pH stable for dry waste and gradually increasing at 6 to 7.4 which is optimum range for pH and methanogenic stage. Mainly pH based on acetogenesis and methanogenesis stages.

V. CONCLUSION

Anaerobic digestion of industrial waste has been carried out in a laboratory large scale floating drum bio digester with two different conditions. The maximum biogas yield was obtained 0.68 m³ from dry waste and methane concentration (CH₄) was reached in 67% compare to wet waste. The acid production pH level was 7.1 end of digestion at observed in dry waste in 45 days. Hence industrial waste was potential source for energy production. The conversion of industrial waste to biogas using anaerobic digestion process represents a viable and commercial one.

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